

Jay Greig was born in Carson City, Nevada in 1980. He is noted [graphite pencil artist](#), who's drawings have been widely published and have won a number of awards in numerous national and international juried shows.

As a graphite pencil artist, his goal is to achieve a photographic level of realism in his subjects, one that makes viewers gasp at the fact that they are looking at a drawing, not in fact a photograph.

This hyperrealist artist works with this medium using different materials, from coloured pencils, to graphite or charcoal. In most cases, he uses the trusty pencil and paper to get his desired results.

American [artist Jay Greig](#) is a master at capturing dark moods and human emotions in the smallest detail. The skill of his pencil is outstanding, whether he is rendering the wrinkles of an elderly man or the tears of a young woman, he achieves transcendence.

Jay Greig is a highly skilled pencil artist, one specialising in graphite realism drawing. His favourite subjects are very often animals, as opposed to humans. The way he manages to sketch the fur of a lion or the pose of a domestic cat, is truly commendable.

He uses solely pencil and paper to get his desired effect. When you gaze fully at his fabulous creations, it is hard to comprehend that the only art instruction that he received was from a drawing instruction manual.

American artist Jay Greig focuses his attention on pencil vehicular portraits. He started to draw cars at the age of 6, and by the time he reached his teenage years he was already drawing his own inventions. He is particularly good at illustrating the reflections that come off metal subjects. He is also master at capturing dark moods and human emotions in the smallest detail. The skill of his pencil is outstanding, whether he is rendering the wrinkles of an elderly man or the tears of a young woman, he achieves transcendence.

Much of [Jay Greig's work](#) is centred on drawing studies and portrait illustration, with an emphasis on a photorealist style. Focusing on a three-dimensional approach her pieces are full of intimacy and longing, exploring the often tentative relationships humans have with each other.